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THE PHARMACOLOGICAL POTENTIAL OF *CAESALPINIA BONDOC*

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ABSTRACT

Caesalpinia bonduc L. is a medicinal plant belonging to the family Caesalpiniaceae. The plant is found in all over India. The plant is a large prickly shrub. It is popular in indigenous system of medicine like Ayurveda, Siddha, Homoeopathy and Unani. In Indian traditional plant medicine, it has been considered as an important remedy for the treatment of several diseases. The plant has been reported to possess antinociceptive, anxiolytic, antidiabetic, antidiarrhoeal, anthelmintic, adaptogenic, anti-inflammatory, antiestrogenic, antimicrobial, antimalarial, antifungal, antioxidant, antispasmodic, antipsoriatic, antiproliferative, antitumor, hepatoprotective, anticonvulsant, larvacidal and antifilarial etc. activities of various parts of *C. bonduc* plant. It can be concluded that *C. bonduc* can become the best source of medicine in future on various ailments with further investigations. Hence attempts have been made to take collect and compile the information about the traditional use of various parts of *C. bonduc* in various ailments, chemical constituents from various parts and the effective use of various extracts for treatment of different diseases.

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INTRODUCTION

The herbal medications play imperative role in the wellbeing framework of people over the world. In treatment, therapeutic plants are utilized in winning sicknesses of the individual as well as potential source to keep up great wellbeing. It is required to comprehend the particular constituents in the herbal medications which are compelling in the diverse treatments. There are numerous verifications showing the significance of herbal plants utilized in the distinctive traditional frameworks.¹ It is seen that numerous restorative plants are utilized to fix ailments like stomach related issues, cardiovascular disorders, metabolic issues, liver issue and the disorders of central nervous systems.² The therapeutic plants are vital in a portion of the treatments traditionally. Phytochemicals are essential for the assurance of plants just as insurance of individuals from different diseases.³ At the most 5% of the 300,000 types of the plants worldwide have been examined experimentally for their therapeutic use. It is seen by the specialists that the developing nations rely upon the medicinal plants to fix the sicknesses especially in the district where there is the absence of hospitals.⁴ *Caesalpinia bonduc* is one of the pantropical leguminous scandent shrubs which is very popular source of medicine since ancient period by the local people and is studied by several workers for their scientific use. *Caesalpinia bonduc* is ordered under the group of Caesalpiniaceae. It is otherwise called *C. bonduc* Flem and *C. crista* Linn. Generally it is called Fever Nut, Bonduc Nut and Nicker Nut also.⁵ In traditional system of Indian, i.e Ayurveda, *Caesalpinia bonduc* (roxb.) is generally utilized for its antiperiodic, antipyretic, calming, anthelmintic, antimalarial and furthermore for various infections like skin ailments, hydrocele, leprosy, spasms, orchitis, paralysis and analogical nervous complaints. It additionally described to have antioxidant, antibacterial, antitumor and antidiabetic actions.⁶ It is valuable to set up the moisturizer for the treatment of agony type cellulitis in Chinese customary medicines.⁷ The goal of the present survey is to highlight the chemical constituents and the pharmacological and therapeutic uses of *Caesalpinia bonduc*.

Synonyms^{2,5}

English: Nicker Seed, Bonduc Nut, Fever Nut, Nicker Nut.

Hindi: Kantikaranja, Sagar Gota, Kantkarej.

Urdu: Aktimakit.

Telugu: Gaccakayai, Mullathige.

Marathi: Gajaga. Unani: Karanjwaa.

Kannada: Kiri gajjuga, gajjga, Gajjekayi.

Tamil Name: Kazarci, Kalarcip paruppu, Kalarciver

Sanskrit Name: Prakiriyā, Vitapakaranja, Kakachika, Varini, Kantakikaranja, Tirini, Valli, Kantakini, Tinagachhika, karanja, Putikaranjah, Lataakaranja, Krakachika and Karanjin.

Geological Distribution:

The plant is found in the tropical and the subtropical regions of Asia⁸. It is disseminated in Srilanka, Bangladesh, Myanmar, China and Vietnam⁹. It is likewise found in Andaman, Nicobar Islands and in India particularly in the tropical region.²

Useful part of the plant: Root, stem, leaves, bark, seeds and nuts are used for medicinal purpose.

Phytoconstituents present:

Whole plant of *Caesalpinia bonduc* contain all major chemical constituents for example, Hydrocarbons, Fatty Acids, Steroidal Saponin, Aminoacids, Phytosterols, Isoflavones, and Phenolics.

Traditional and modern uses:

The seed is claimed to be styptic, laxative and anthelmintic and fixes irritations, valuable in malaria, colic, hydrocele, skin illnesses and leprosy. In Madras (Chennai) an ointment is delivered utilizing the powdered seeds with castor oil and applied externally in hydrocele and orchitis.¹⁰⁻¹³ The seeds are viewed as tonic, anthelmintic, febrifuge, antibleorrhagic, and explicit in the therapy of hydrocele. The oil from the seeds is used in convulsions and paralysis. In Guinea, the beat seeds are seen as vesicant. The powdered seeds were blended with equivalent piece of pepper powder to malaria patients and were found to have weak antiperiodic properties. In malignant malaria, they didn't do any great. The seeds are ground in water and given internally in snake-bite. The seeds are not an anti-dote to snake-venom.¹⁴⁻¹⁵ Seed and long pepper powders taken with honey gives great expectorant impact. Consumed seeds with alum and consumed arecanut are a decent dentifrice helpful in elastic gums, gum boils, and so on. In West Indies, the cooked seeds are utilized as hostile to diabetic.^{10, 16} The kernel of the seed is very helpful and important in every single common instance of basic, proceeded and irregular fevers. The kernel powder blended with a balance of dark pepper is taken thrice daily in a portion of 15-30 grains by grown-ups and 3-4 grains by children. It was made authority in the Indian Pharmaceutical Codex 16 the portion of the powder being 15-18 grains. It is said to deliver lot of sweat, prompting the decrease of fever. Kernel powder with sugar and goat milk gives great outcome results in liver disorder.¹⁷ Extract of roasted kernels was utilized in asthma. Kids unable to process mother's milk were given the concentrate of the kernel or its powder alongside ginger, salt and nectar to get great stomachic impact. Paste made from kernel gives alleviation from boils and other such swellings. A cake prepared of thirty grains of powdered kernels, seared in ghee taken two times every day is a significant cure in cases of acute orchitis, ovaritis and scrofula. Root in La Reunion and Madagascar, the roots are viewed as febrifuge and anthelmintic, they are mostly utilized as an astringent in leucorrhoea and blennorrhagia.^{10,12,13,16,18} In Guinea, a decoction of the root is recommended in fever.

The root-bark is useful for tumors and for evacuating the placenta after child birth.¹⁴ Bark of root has number of characteristics like febrifuge, intestinal worms, amenorrhoea, cough, and anthelmintic and so on. In Jamaica, it is utilized as rubifacient and as a local application for wounds. Leaves and twigs are generally utilized for the treatment of tumors, inflammation and liver issue. They have additionally been used for treatment of toothache. Leaves and squeezes have been utilized customarily for elephantiasis and smallpox.

PHARMACOLOGICAL STUDIES

In spite of the fact that a great deal of pharmacological examinations have been completed based on the ingredients presence a significantly more can even now be investigated, exploited and used. An outline of the findings of these investigations is presented below.

Antioxidant activity

The ethanolic concentrate of *C. bonducella* seeds contained good level of phenolic constituents and were prepared for repressing, quenching free radicals to cease the radical chain reaction, and acting as reducing agents.¹⁹ The potential antioxidant activity was confirmed by DPPH for ethanol leaf extract of *Caesalpinia bonduc*. The results demonstrate that the antioxidant activity may add to the cytotoxic nature of the plant which may be the future study to be carried out.²⁰ Chloroform extract of *Caesalpinia bonducella* seeds shows antioxidant activity.²¹ The phenolic compounds of *C. bonduc* leaves and twigs extract could be major contributors to its antioxidant activity. The ethanolic extract of the leaves and twigs of *C. bonduc* has significant catalase and peroxidase activity. It is therefore suggested that it might have antioxidant properties comparable to known standards.²²

Antiproliferative activity

Isolated Cassane diterpenes from *Caesalpinia bonduc*. The isolated compounds were checked for their antiproliferative activity against MCF-7 (breast adenocarcinoma), DU145 (prostate carcinoma), C33A (Cervical carcinoma) and Vero (African green monkey kidney fibroblast) cells.²³

Anticancer

Caesalpinia bonduc is compared with already established anti-cancer drugs, the binding energy was highly comparable as well as interactions with the proteins. They further possess good ADMET characteristics, indicating these phytochemical isolates can likewise be viewed as safe and thus be further developed into active commercial anti-cancer drugs.²⁴ The methanol extract of *C. bonducella* leaves was assessed for the antitumor activity in Ehrlich ascites carcinoma (EAC) - bearing Swiss albino mice. It caused noticeable reduction in the volume of tumor, packed cell volume and viable cell count and it extended the life of EAC- tumor affected mice. It is watched that MECB plays very significant role as antioxidant and antitumor activity in EAC- affected mice.²⁵

Induces Apoptosis

Methanol Extract of *Caesalpinia bonducella* at 200 mg/kg concentration was responsible of decrease in the entire % of viable EAT cells (51.6 percent and ascites volume (65 percent) in treated mice. MECB expanded the rate of apoptosis with progressively number of cells showing characteristic properties, for example, membrane blebbing, apoptotic body development and fragmented DNA which was obvious by Giemsa and Acridine orange/Ethidium bromide (AO/EB) staining. Also, the mice survival time was expanded upon MECB treatment. In addition, FACS information proposes that death of MECB treated EAT cells was because of apoptosis and not by necrosis. Besides the examination for molecular mechanism uncovered MECB diminished the level of apoptotic Bcl-2 expression while expanding pro-apoptotic Bax level. These results confirm the antiproliferative and pro-apoptotic activity of MECB.²⁶

Antiviral activity

An ethanolic extract of the root and stem exhibited activity against the Vaccinia virus.²⁷ Anti-Amyloidogenic/Alzheimer's disease *Caesalpinia* leaf aqueous extract has anti-amyloidogenic potential. Study showed aqueous extract of Latakaranj could inhibit the Abeta aggregation from monomers and oligomers and able to disintegrate the preformed fibrils.²⁸

Adaptogenic activity

Adaptogenic activity of *Caesalpinia bonduc* seed extracts in rats was reported by utilizing cold stress and swim endurance model. It demonstrated that the concentrates significantly increased the swim endurance time. Stress induced animals showed hypoglycaemia as well as exhaustion in serum cortisol level and expanded leukocyte count, the concentrates demonstrated a significant activity in defeating these imbalances.²⁹

Anti-hepatotoxic activity

Treatment with *Caesalpinia bonduc* separate recuperated the harmed liver to ordinary after 24 hrs at a dose of 500 mg/kg which show that *Caesalpinia bonduc* has antihepatotoxic impact. The conceivable antihepatotoxic mechanism of *Caesalpinia bonduc* has not been accounted for yet. It is accepted that the impact of *Caesalpinia bonduc* extricate on liver protection is identified with glutathione-interceded detoxification as well as free radical suppressing activity.³⁰ C.bonduc extract increased the concentration of glutathione in liver and glutathione in blood and liver Na+K+ ATPase movement fundamentally when contrasted with its paracetamol treated control group.

Treatment with C. bonduc extract decreased the increased level of serum ALT, AST, ALP and bilirubin, which appear to offer the protection and keep up the functional integrity of hepatic cells. Extract of C. bonduc managed protection from such paracetamol prompted liver harm. C. bonduc extract is a promising hepatoprotective agent.³¹

Anticataract Activity

The ethanolic extract of seed kernals of *Caesalpinia bonducella*.(L) Fleming has anticataract and antioxidant activities, which might be useful to prevent or decreasing the progress of cataract.The extract reduced opacity and tissue malondehyde (MDA) level and raised catalase and superoxide dismutase (SOD) activities. There was increase in water soluble protein levels and total proteins.³²

Anti-inflammatory and pain relieving Action

Oral management of cbsce at different doses produces consistent antinociceptive and anti-inflammatory impacts in various models of torment and inflammation. The Anti-inflammatory action shown by the extract of the seed coat can be credited to the presence of triterpenoidal moieties in the seed coat extricate. Propose that CBSCE has solid peripheral antinociceptive activity.³³ The impact was dose-dependent at 30 and 100 mg of *Caesalpinia bonduc* flower extract. At 300 mg/kg level, CBFE demonstrated significant reduce in granuloma weight showing concealment of proliferative stage by extract.³⁵ The *Caesalpinia bonducella* in water form exerts analgesic impact like nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. The anti-nociceptive action shown by *Caesalpinia bonducella* in aqua form on hot plate and acetic acid prompted squirming test may possess centrally and peripherally mediated anti-nociceptive properties.³⁴

Antipyretic activity

The *Caesalpinia bonducella* seed kernel extract showed marked antipyretic action against Brewer's yeast-initiated pyrexia in rats. The concentrate had good central analgesic action in hot plate and tail flick methods. In conclusion, the study suggested that the ethanolic extract of *Caesalpinia bonducella* seed kernel has strong antipyretic and antinociceptive activities and thus, approves its utilization in the treatment of pain and pyretic disorders.³⁶ The seed oil of C. bonducella is good source for antipyretic agent.³⁷

Antibacterial & antimicrobial activity

The antibacterial activities of the methanol extract and ethyl acetic acid, chloroform, and pet. ether portions of the C. bonducella leaves obtained by the disc diffusion technique. The chloroform portion exhibited better antimicrobial action at all 3 concentrations (300, 500, and 800 µg/disc) against almost all bacteria. The methanol extricate shown the lowest antibacterial action followed by the ethyl acetic acid and pet. ether fractions. The methanol crude extract and the ethyl acetic acid, pet. ether, and chloroform fractions of C. Bonducella have better antimicrobial exercises against specific microorganisms at different doses.³⁸ *Caesalpinia bonducella* seed extracts showed significant antibacterial activity with low MIC values.³⁹ Simin et al. has reported Antimicrobial action of seed separates and bondenolide from *Caesalpinia bonduc* (L.) Roxb. The antibacterial and antifungal actions, alongside a phytotoxicity trial of the recently isolated diterpene bondenolide (1), of a methanol extract, ethylacetate division and water soluble part of the methanol concentrate of *Caesalpinia bonduc* (L.) Roxb were assayed.⁴⁰ The antimicrobial activities exhibited by extracts revealed that, the *Caesalpinia bonduc* is a potentially good source of bioactive metabolites for development of broad spectrum antibiotics.⁴¹

Antifungal Activity

The aqueous and ethyl acetic acid extracts of C.bonducella seeds show high to moderate antifungal activity against *Alternaria solani*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*. It indicates C. bonducella possesses a potential to control important fungal pathogens. It might be because of the presence of a few bioactive molecules that include oils, saponins, sterols, glycosides, tannins, alkaloids, phenols, resins and flavonoides in seeds of C. bonducella.⁴²

Antipsoriatic activity

Plant has certainly antipsoriatic action which is in concurrence with its traditional use. CBHAW (water fraction of *Caesalpinia bonduc* hydroalcoholic extract) is the main portion that demonstrated great activity in the mouse tail experiment, antiproliferant action and lipoxygenase inhibition assay.⁴³ Leaves of *Caesalpinia bonduc* have been utilized by traditional siddha healer of Malabar locale for psoriasis treatment.⁴⁴ Anthelmintic activity. This examination uncovered that petroleum ether, chloroform and ethanol extract of *C. bonduc* STEM BARK showed significant Anthelmintic action against *Pheretimaposthuma* in dose depended manner when compared to control and very similar to the standard drug. The extract were altogether effective in paralyzing and killing earthworm (*Pheretimaposthuma*).⁴⁵ Jabbar et al. has first time reported anthelmintic action in *Caesalpinia bonducella* by in-vitro and in-vivo, they legitimized their utilization in the conventional medicinal system of Pakistan.⁴⁶

Anthelmintic action of leaves of *Caesalpinia bonducella* was examined for their anthelmintic action against *Phertima posthuma* and *Ascaridia galli*. Variuos concen- trations were used in bioassay. Both extracts showed significant anthelmintic activity.⁴⁷

Larvicidal activity

Saravanan KS, et al., reported Mosquito larvicidal properties of different concentrate of leaves and fixed oil from the seeds of *Caesalpinia bonduc* (L) Roxb. A primer research was undertaken to decide the efficacies of petroleum ether, ethanolic, aqueous extracts of dried leaves and fixed oil from the seeds of *Caesalpinia bonduc* (L). Roxb at different concentrations against the 4th instar larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus* by who rules.

Hundred percent mortality was seen in 1% concentration of P.ether and ethanolic concentrate of leaf, though it was 55 percent in 2.5 percent concentration of aqueous concentrate and 92.6 percent in 2.5 percent concentration of fixed oil. The main constituent in charge of the mortality is to be isolated to think of a promising larvicidal agent, which will be economic, non-pollutant and ecofriendly.⁴⁸

Antifilarial activity

C. bonducella-seed part demonstrated microfilaricidal, macrofilaricidal and female-sterilizing adequacy against *L. sigmodontis* and microfilaricidal and female-sterilizing viability against *B. malayi* in animal models, demonstrating the capability of this plant in giving a lead to new antifilarial tranquilize development.⁴⁹

Antimalarial Activity

Cold ethanol, aqueous and hot ethanol extracts of seeds of *Caesalpinia bonducella* showed 56%, 65% and 76% growth inhibition of *P. falciparum* respectively. It supports antimalarial activity of *C. bonducella*.⁵⁰ Three new cassane furanoditerpenoids (1-3) together with known cassane diterpenes were secluded from the seed kernels of *Caesalpinia bonduc*. Compounds 1-3 shown great antimalarial action against multidrug resistant K1 strain of *Plasmodium falciparum*.⁵¹ CbTI- 2 was highly poisonous towards erythrocytic attack of *P. falciparum* merozoites and denied these activities in a dose dependent way. The harmful activity of CbTI- 2 on development and multiplication of *P. falciparum* was additionally apparent.⁵²

Antifeedant activity

The hexane, chloroform and ethyl acetic acid extracts of *C. bonduc* showed antifeedant action in a concentration dependent manner.⁵³ The noctuid *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) is a polyphagous pest and assaults more than 200 crop species in India. *Caesalpinia crista* seed extracts were explored in the research facility against *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner). The extracts showed powerful antifeedant and growth interruption action. Among the different extract of *Caesalpinia crista*, maximum antifeedance is caused by methanolic extract, followed by hexane extract, ethyl acetate extract, butanol extract and aqueous extract.⁵⁴ Antidiarrhoeal activity: The methanol, ethyl acetic acid, chloroform, and petroleum ether concentrate of leaves of *C. bonducella* at a portion of 400 mg/kg showed a significant inhibition of castor oil prompted diarrhoea in concentrate dependent manner in experimental rats.⁵⁵ Anti-ulcer Activity: The aqueous extract of *C. bonducella* played very important role in curing ulcer and show antisecretory effect. There is scope to use this plant to treat gastric disorders. The extract also noticeably decreased the gastric volume, total and free acidity, and raised the pH of the gastric fluid. The existence of saponins, alkaloids, triterpenes, flavonoids, steroids and tannins was detected in the aqueous extract of CBD and it was found that flavonoides possessed anti-ulcer activity. The methanolic extract of *C. bonducella* (Linn.) Flem. leaves have considerable anti- ulcer activity.⁵⁶

Antispasmodic activity

Khan HU, et. al., have been reported antibacterial, antifungal, antispasmodic and Ca⁺⁺ antagonist effects of *Caesalpinia bonducella*.⁵⁷

Anticonvulsant activity

Pet.ether extract of *Caesalpinia bonduc*(PCMB) at medium and higher doses (600 & 800mg/kg) exhibited a significant anti-convulsive effect as evidenced from increased onset time of seizures and decreased duration of tonic-clonic seizures. PECB at 600 and 800mg/kg had deferred the beginning of clonus seizures and diminished the span of tonic extensor stage and offered a dose-dependent protection and exhibited significant anticonvulsant activity. The anticonvulsant effect produced by PECB might be through suppression of the action of strychnine on glycine inhibitory mechanisms. Confirmed the anticonvulsant activity of PECB in mice.⁵⁸

Anxiolytic activities

In Stair-case model, all the 3 dosages i.e low, medium and high 400, 600 and 800mg/kg of PECB had demonstrated a good and dose dependent Anxiolytic action by increasing the quantity of steps climbed with no tremendous impact on rearings by all these three dosages. So also in EPM test medium and high dosages, however not the low portion of PECB had significantly increased both number of entries and time spent in open arms and diminished in number of entries and time spent in shut arms. In Hole-board model, medium and high portions 600 and 800mg/kg yet not the low dosage 400mg/kg of PECB had significantly increased the number, latency and the time of head dipping but not the rearings. Anyway in LDT demonstrate high dosages 800mg/kg of PECB had essentially shown anxiolytic action by enhancing time spent, number of crossings in light compartment and diminished the time spent in dull compartment and diminished the quantity of rearings in both light and dim compartments. In OFT models, medium and high dosages 600 and 800mg/kg yet not the low portion 400mg/kg of PECB had significantly increased absolute motion, central locomotion, number of grooming yet the immobility time has definitely reduced.⁵⁹

Neuroprotective activity

The methanolic and aqueous extract of *Caesalpinia bonducella* (Roxb) has shown significantly neuroprotective activity compare to the standard drug (Vitamin E). Different extracts of the *Caesalpinia bonducella* (Roxb) exerts remarkable antioxidant activity due to possible multiple effects involving significant protection against the oxidative damage, which might be credited to its protective activity on lipid peroxidation and resistance adding to the assurance against oxidative damage.⁶⁰

Nootropic Activity

The potential of dried seed kernels of *Caesalpinia crista* extract as learning and memory strengthener was undertaken. In mice, amnesic result of scopolamine was ameliorated using aqueous extract of dried seed kernels of *Caesalpinia crista*. Using the radial arm maze and Morris water maze paradigm as the exteroceptive behavioral models, aqueous extract of dried seed kernels of *Caesalpinia crista* linn. is compared with standard drug piracetam in scopolamine induced amnesia in mice. Morris water maze model for learning and memory and radial arm maze model for learning and memory retention was carried out with the statistical analysis.⁶¹

Hepatoprotective activity

The animals treated with hydro alcoholic concentrate of *Caesalpinia bonducella* leaves demonstrated liver security against the toxicant as apparent by the presence of ordinary hepatic cords, nonappearance of necrosis and lesser fatty invasion. The hydro alcoholic extract is a good herbal hepatoprotective agent. The conceivable explanation behind this action might be the presence of flavonoid and phenolic compounds as secondary metabolites in the leaf extract.⁶² The co-administration of CB extract and CCl4 significantly improved the condition by decreasing the serum AST, ALT, ALP, bilirubin and total protein significantly in preventive and curative groups respectively. This indicates the effectiveness of the CB in maintaining the structural and functional integrity of the hepatocellular components. The histopathological findings likewise propose that the treatment with CB extract can restore the liver architecture in CCl4 induced liver cirrhosis in rats. CCl4 induced fatty degeneration; necrosis and fibrosis of liver can be prevented /repaired by administration of CB.⁶³

Hypolipidemic activity

EESKCB (ethanolic concentrate of seed kernel of *Caesalpinia bonducella*) with high fat diet showed significant decrease in all the lipid parameters except HDL. The lipid lowering activity of the extract might be because of the presence of triterpenoids, polyphenols, flavonoids and saponins in it. Sitosterol, constituent of seed kernel of *Caesalpinia bonducella*, has been reported to possess hypocholesterolemic action by inhibiting the intestinal absorption of cholesterol and accelerating the catabolism of cholesterol to bile acid. The extract inhibited the gain in body weight probably by restoring the composition of the gut microflora and thereby inhibiting hepatic lipogenesis and lipoprotein lipase activity.⁶⁴

Anticancer activity

The methanol extract of *Caesalpinia bonducella* FLEMING (*Caesalpinia* leaves (MECB) were evaluated for antitumor activity against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma (EAC)-bearing Swiss albino mice. This examination deals with the impact of MECB on the development of transplantable murine tumor, life length of EAC-bearing hosts, hematological profile, and biochemical parameters, for example, lipid peroxidation (LPO), glutathione content (GSH), superoxide dismutase (SOD), and catalase (CAT) activities. MECB caused huge ($P < 0.01$) decline in tumor volume, packed cell volume, and viable cell count; and it delayed the life expectancy of EAC-tumor bearing mice. The outcomes show that MECB displayed significant antitumor and antioxidant action in EAC-bearing mice.⁶⁵

Immunomodulatory activity

Caesalpinia bonducella is a strong immunostimulant, stimulating both specific and nonspecific immune mechanisms. The administration of ethanolic seed concentrate of *Caesalpinia bonducella* fundamentally enhanced the all-out WBCs count, RBCs count, hemoglobin, and platelets number and furthermore reestablished the myelosuppressive impacts induced by cyclophosphamide.⁶⁶ The assessment of immunomodulatory potential of ethanolic extract of seed of *C. bonducella* caused noticeable increase in percent neutrophil adhesion to nylon fibers. *C. bonducella* contain immunomodulatory activity and it can be used to prevent autoimmune ailments.⁶⁷ Investigation of the aqueous concentrate of *C. bonducella* seeds on cell intervened and humoral components of the immune system in rats delivered an increase in hemagglutinating antibody titer and a change in delayed-type hypersensitivity recommending that the concentrate could be a promising immunostimulatory agent.⁶⁸ The evaluation of immunomodulatory potential by oral organization of ethanolic seed concentrate of *Caesalpinia bonducella* (200-500 mg/kg) evoked a significant increment in percent neutrophil adhesion to nylon filaments. It likewise demonstrated the dose dependent increase in antibody titre values.⁶⁹

Diuretic activity

Both the aqueous and methanol concentrates of *C. bonduc* demonstrated a dose-dependent rise in urine discharge. As for the aqueous concentrate, the maximum increase in urinary excretion was created at 300 mg/kg compared with the methanol extract. Study provide a quantitative basis to explain the traditional use of *C. bonduc* as a diuretic agent in Moroccan population.⁷⁰

Anti-diabetic activity

In diabetic rats, both the polar concentrates (ethyl acetic acid and aqueous) as well as glibenclamide, demonstrated good hypoglycaemic impact, besides, reversing the diabetes induced changes in lipid and liver glycogen levels. To the extent the non-polar concentrates were concerned, the ether extricate demonstrated a minor antidiabetic action, while the petroleum ether extract unsuccessful to indicate any.⁷¹ Watery, ethanol and chloroform extracts had demonstrated good protection and brought down the blood glucose levels to ordinary in glucose tolerance test. In alloxan prompted diabetic rats the greatest decline in blood glucose was seen after 3h at a dose level of 250 mg/kg of body weight. In long term treatment of alloxan prompted diabetic rats, the level of assurance was determined by assessing blood glucose, triglycerides, cholesterol and urea levels on 0,3,5,7 and tenth day.⁷²

The oral administration of the petroleum ether and ethanolic seed concentrates of *Caesalpinia bonducella* (300 mg/kg) delivered huge antihyperglycemic activity as well as it brought down the BUN levels significantly.⁷³ The hydroalcoholic concentrate of *Caesalpinia bonducella* seed diminished blood glucose levels fundamentally in normal mice, hyperglycemia mice and alloxan-initiated diabetic mice.⁷⁴ Hydroethanolic concentrate of *Caesalpinia bonducella* seed demonstrated that it diminished fasting blood glucose levels.⁷⁵ *Caesalpinia bonducella* leaves extracts effectively reduced plasma GOT (Glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase), GPT (glutamic pyruvic transaminase), LDH (Locate dehydronase) activities in diabetic rats, suggesting that the hydroalcoholic extracts of *Caesalpinia bonducella* leaves may prevent hepatic injury associated with diabetes.⁷⁶

Antispermatogetic activity

Oral organization of aqueous concentrate of seeds of *Caesalpinia bonduc* (L.) Roxb. (Caesalpiniaceae) brought about 40% decrease in sperm count. The treatment results in slow decline of normal sperm thickness from 27.63 (Million/MI) in charge to 25.11, 20.63 and 16.63 at the dose of 50, 100 and 150 mg/kg respectively. The outcomes demonstrated that the seed extricate significantly diminished sperm density and rat's show (9.06%), (25.29%) and (39.79%) normal enhance in antispermatogetic activity with increasing dose of concentrations.⁷⁷

Sperm effect

Investigation of graded doses of alcoholic seed extract of *C. bonducella* demonstrated morphological changes in the sperm of lbino rats. The effect can be a direct result of general unsettling influences in proteins and change in the cauda epididymal milieu, most likely because of androgen insufficiency secondary to *C. bonducella* treatment.⁷⁸

Antiestrogenic activity

Kanchan R,et al., results proposed that alcohol seed concentrate of *Caesalpinia bonducella* has antiestrogenic property,possibly acting through inhibition of estrogen secretion.⁷⁹ Abortifacient Activity In rural India, the seeds of *c. bonducella* are used traditionally in the fertility regulations in females. The leaves are utilized as an emmenagogue and to smooth out the conveyance in pregnant ladies. The blend of seed powder of *C. bonducella* and sesame oil brings about abortion. It implies that the plant has abortifacient activity.⁸⁰

Anti-fertility activity

The administration of test drug *Caesalpinia bonduc* exhibite potent antiimplantation activity, anti-estrogenic activity, abortion and anti-estrogenic activity, antiovlutary activity. *Caesalpinia bonduc* Linn. Roxb. Root bark (ERb) can be used for induction in sterility i.e. it can be used as anti-fertility agent.⁸¹

CONCLUSION

From the various scientific research based on *Caesalpinia bonduc*, the plant has a huge biological potential. Several chemicals present in the plant shows a wide pharmacological and medicinal property. More research and evaluation needs to be done to isolate and identify different chemicals present in the plant which will be used for innumerable application for human welfare in the near future. Search grant from Department of Science and Technology, Government of India under the WOS-A scheme.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

The author Vinesh Prasad Vadlakonda obtained the data, analyzed the data and compiled the data in proper manner and computed the data as per journals instructions. The author Mrs. Sugandha G. Chaudhari given guidance about review article.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Conflict of interest declared none.

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